

The Algebra of the Equality on Complex Numbers I

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Abstract

The manuscript establish the properties of $Add_{map}(a_1, a_2) = a_1 + a_2$ homomorphism over a monoid of Complex numbers to explain the relation $-a_1 =_A a_1$ and the inequality $-1 < 1$

Keyword: Complex; Homomorphism; Monoid; Algebra; Equivalence
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1 Introduction

Argand's Product establish next equality:

$$(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = (ac - bd, ad + bc)$$

When the terms of both entries are sum we have:

$$(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = ac - bd + ad + bc$$

Now suppose that \exists a function $Add_{map} : C \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ such that

$$Add_{map}(a, b) = a + b$$

On Argand's product we have:

$$Add_{map}[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] =$$

$$Add_{map}(ac - bd, ad + bc) =$$

$$ac - bd + ad + bc < ac + bd + ad + bc$$

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hence

$$\begin{aligned}ac &= ac \\ad &= ad \\bc &= bc \\-bd &< bd\end{aligned}$$

Lets note the next property about Cartesian plane and the unit squares form on quadrants I and II.

Figure 1: Diagram 1. Cartesian plane with coordinates

Square quadrant I

Sides: $(1, 0)$ and $(0, 1)$

$$\begin{aligned}Area_{QI} &= Side_x \cdot Side_y = (1) \cdot (1) = \sqrt{(1-0)^2 + (0-0)^2} \cdot \sqrt{(0-0)^2 + (1-0)^2} \\&= \sqrt{(1)^2} \cdot \sqrt{(1)^2}\end{aligned}$$

Square quadrant II

Sides: $(-1, 0)$ and $(0, 1)$

$$\begin{aligned}Area_{QII} &= Side_x \cdot Side_y = (-1) \cdot (1) = \sqrt{(0-1)^2 + (0-0)^2} \cdot \sqrt{(0-0)^2 + (1-0)^2} \\&= \sqrt{(-1)^2} \cdot \sqrt{(1)^2}\end{aligned}$$

Intuitively we know that areas of squares must be equal hence next equality must be proposed:

$$Area_{QI} = Area_{QII}$$

then

$$(1) \cdot (1) = (-1) \cdot (1)$$

cancelling from both sides equal terms we have:

$$1 = -1$$

This property is not very well discussed on bibliography, due to the use of Euclidean distance to assign values to the sides of some polygon and the incapacity to discuss next two problems:

1) equality between two quantities that are different; i.e. when $a \neq b$; where we can conclude intuitively that $a = b$ like before.

2) The meaning of negative distances and values of areas (i.e. negative values for geometrical properties).

On this work, this property could explain next fact about $Add(a, b)$ function and Argand's product:

If

$$1 = -1$$

Multiplying from both sides for bd we have

$$bd = -bd \dots(a)$$

and hence the four terms obtained on inequality of Add_{map} becomes equalities.

Henceforth can be established that:

$$ac - bd + ad + bc = ac + bd + ad + bc$$

Developing right terms we will have:

$$ac + bd + ad + bc = (a + b) \cdot (c + d)$$

$$= Add_{map}(a, b) \cdot Add_{map}(c, d)$$

Therefore

$$Add_{map}[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] = Add_{map}(a, b) \cdot Add_{map}(c, d)$$

The distributive property about $Add(a, b)$ function is established through next property about homomorphism of groups:

$$f(g_1 * g_2) = f(g_1) \cdot f(g_2); \forall g_1, g_2 \in G$$

when $*$ and \cdot binary operation are the Argand's Product and the Cartesian product respectively.

On this work the kind of equality established on (a) will be represented with next sign:

$$=_A := \text{Abstract meaning}$$

2 Homomorphism of Monoids for Add_{map} function

First lets prove that (C, \cdot) form a monoid.

a) (C, \cdot) is associative

$$\begin{aligned} & [(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] \cdot (e, f) = \\ & [ac - bd, ad + bc] \cdot (e, f) = \\ & [(ac - bd)e - (ad + bc)f, (ac - bd)f + (ad + bc)e] = \\ & [ace - bde - adf - bcf, acf - bdf + ade + bce] = \\ & [ace - adf - cfb - deb, acf + ade + bce - bdf] = \\ & [a(ce - df) - (cf + de)b, a(cf + de) + b(ce - df)] = \\ & (a, b) \cdot [ce - df, cf + de] = \\ & (a, b) \cdot [(c, d) \cdot (e, f)] \end{aligned}$$

hence \cdot is associative

b) (C, \cdot) have identity element

$$(e_1, e_2) \cdot (c, d) = (c, d) \cdot (e_1, e_2) = (e_1c - e_2d, e_1d + e_2c)$$

If

$$e_1 = 1 \text{ and } e_2 = 0$$

Hence

$$(e_1c - e_2d, e_1d + e_2c) = (c, d)$$

Later we have on the right

$$\begin{aligned} (c, d) \cdot (e_1, e_2) &= (ce_1 - de_2, ce_2 + de_1) \\ &= (c, d) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$(e_1, e_2) = (1, 0) = e_C \in C \text{ is the identity element}$$

To fulfilled whole properties about homomorphism is necessary to defined next property:

$$c) \text{ Add}_{map}(e_C) = e_{\mathfrak{R}}$$

$$\text{Add}_{map}(1, 0) = (1 + 0) = 1 = e_{\mathfrak{R}prod}$$

being last the identity multiplicative in \mathfrak{R} keeping any relationship with usual sum operation defined for real numbers.

The characteristics of Cartesian plane and Add_{map} function establish next axiom about abstract equality.

Property 1. $-b =_A b \in \mathfrak{R}$ iff $-b < b \in \mathfrak{R}$ with $b \neq 0$

3 Congruence Relation $=_A$ and Add_{map}

Def. Any homomorphism $f : X \rightarrow Y$ defines a relation \sim on X by $a \sim b$ if and only if $f(a) = f(b)$. The relation \sim is called the kernel of f . It is a compatible relation on X .

Def. A relation R on a given algebraic structure is called compatible if for each n and each n -ary operation μ defined on the structure: whenever $a_1 R a'_1$ and ... and $a_n R a'_n$, then $\mu(a_1, \dots, a_n) R \mu(a'_1, \dots, a'_n)$.

Proof. a) \supset

With $n = 2$ and $R := <$

$$a_1 < a'_1$$

$$a_2 < a'_2 \dots (a)$$

By trichotomy $a_1 \leq a_2$; $a_1 > a_2$; on monoid equality will be discarded hence

$$a_1 R a'_1 ; a_2 R a'_2$$

And we obtain (a_1, a'_1) , (a_2, a'_2) by Cartesian product property define on next property:

$$R = \{(a_1, a'_1) : (a_1, a'_1) \in A_1 \times A_2 \wedge R(a_1, a'_1) = True\}$$

Applying Add_{map} function we have

$Add_{map}(a_1, a_2) = a_1 + a_2 < a'_1 + a'_2 = Add_{map}(a'_1, a'_2)$; while last inequality is due to (a).

If

$$a_1 + a_2 = \alpha c - \beta d + \alpha d + \beta c$$

and

$$a'_1 + a'_2 = \alpha c + \beta d + \alpha d + \beta c$$

and by

Area Square Quadrant $I =$ Area Square Quadrant II next equalities fulfilled

$$Add_{map}(a_1, a_2) =$$

$$Add_{map}[(\alpha c - \beta d, \alpha d + \beta c)] = Add_{map}[(\alpha, \beta) \cdot (c, d)]$$

$$=_{A} Add_{map}(\alpha, \beta) \cdot Add_{map}(c, d) = (\alpha + \beta) \cdot (c + d)$$

$$= \alpha c + \beta d + \alpha d + \beta c = \text{Add}_{map}(a'_1, a'_2)$$

Therefore

$$\text{Add}_{map}(a_1, a_2) =_A \text{Add}_{map}(a'_1, a'_2)$$

b) \subset

Let be

$$\text{Add}_{map}(a_1, a_2) =_A \text{Add}_{map}(a'_1, a'_2)$$

Hence

$$\text{Add}_{map}(a_1, a_2) < \text{Add}_{map}(a'_1, a'_2)$$

Developing

$$a_1 + a_2 < a'_1 + a'_2$$

If

$$a_1 < a'_1$$

and

$$a_2 < a'_2$$

Henceforth

Add_{map} homomorphism defines a relation $=_A$ on \mathfrak{R} through the relation $<$

4 References

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